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**«PRACTICAL USE OF THE QUIZLET ONLINE SERVICE IN TEACHING
FOREIGN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY: EXPERIENCE, RESULTS, AND
EFFECTIVENESS»**

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***Abstract.** This study examines the use of **Quizlet** for learning foreign language vocabulary. **92 first-year students** at M. Utemisov West Kazakhstan University participated. The experimental group used Quizlet, while the control group followed traditional methods. Results showed a **24% increase in vocabulary acquisition** and **15% improvement in grammar tasks** for the Quizlet group. Formats like **Flashcards, Matching, and Quiz** enhanced motivation, engagement, and self-paced learning. Despite minor technical challenges, Quizlet proved to be an effective tool for improving vocabulary, supporting autonomous learning, and developing overall language competence.*

***Keywords:** Quizlet, mobile applications, vocabulary, English language, case studies, internet resources, web technologies, communication technologies, education.*

Introduction

Modern education is undergoing an active phase of digitalization, which opens up wide opportunities for the introduction of innovative technologies into the learning process. This is particularly evident in the field of foreign language teaching, where the use of online resources is becoming an important condition for improving the quality and effectiveness of learning. One of the key tasks in learning a foreign language is mastering vocabulary, since it is vocabulary that serves as the basis for the development of all types of speech activity. In line with this, Grut argues that vocabulary has a definite bearing on reading, listening, speaking, and writing. For example, a person must learn at least 5,000 words to understand non-specialized texts [1, pp. 56-76]. Traditional methods of working with vocabulary, such as memorizing word lists or using flashcards, do not always ensure a high level of motivation and long-term memorization. In this regard, it is becoming increasingly relevant to turn to interactive services that combine elements of gamification, visualization, and independent work. One of the most popular and accessible tools is the online service Quizlet, which allows you to create and use sets of flashcards, tests, and game exercises that promote more effective acquisition of foreign language vocabulary.

The active learning method involves students actively acquiring knowledge (motivation, interest, use of active learning tools). The active learning method is based on constructivist learning theory, which asserts that people learn by creating their own knowledge, connecting ideas and experiences with existing knowledge [2, pp. 14-15]. In his work, Piaget explains that constructivism does not recognize either external preliminary influences (empiricism) or innate abilities (innateness), but rather implies the continuous overcoming of successive stages of learning, when the educational emphasis is based on spontaneous aspects of student activity [3, pp. 10-11].

Active teaching methods in English language teaching are methods that aim to stimulate critical thinking and are characterized by a high degree of interactivity, motivation, and emotional perception of the learning process. The use of active methods in teaching involves students in research, simulation, evaluation, and creative communication activities. The main active teaching methods are problem-based learning (PBL), case-based learning (CBL), and team-based learning (TBL).

It is argued that the use of technology in the classroom is actually beneficial in the sense that it can motivate students and engage them in learning [4, p. 132]. In addition, the development of technology allows foreign language teachers to use it easily.

As S.S. Kunanbaeva notes in the 'Concept of foreign language education of the Republic of Kazakhstan', one of the main directions of improving the training of pedagogical staff in foreign language is 'mastering modern methods and technologies, including information and computer-based, of foreign language teaching' [5,p.29].

Talapova A.K. and Turar A.S. conducted an empirical study on the effectiveness of using the Quizlet online platform to expand vocabulary in foreign language learning. In their work, they showed that Quizlet's interactive features (gamification, flashcards, games) contribute to increasing student engagement and motivation, as well as improving vocabulary acquisition results in the learning process. The results of the study indicate that Quizlet has a significant positive impact on vocabulary memorization and retention, confirming the practical value of online services in foreign language teaching in a digital educational environment [6].

A E. Niyazova in the article 'Using the online application Quizlet for mastering lexical material in teaching foreign languages' the author analyses the advantages and disadvantages of Quizlet in teaching vocabulary. The study is based on examples of using Quizlet in universities of Kazakhstan. [7,pp.13-15].

A detailed study of the Quizlet application was conducted to measure its effectiveness in vocabulary learning, see its impact on rapid vocabulary acquisition, and explore EFL learners' views on using Quizlet. Despite several studies on Quizlet, there is currently a lack of descriptive qualitative research on Quizlet at the highest level, which is particularly relevant to the search for student responses. This gap needs to be filled, as it can enrich knowledge about the use of digital tools for vocabulary acquisition through the Google Classroom program by students at Taraz Regional University. In addition, the issue of integrating technology into the classroom is prevalent and attracts many scholars. The primary reason for choosing this site was the fact that Quizlet is a modern website that allows users to learn vocabulary using flashcards and various educational games. It is also available for Android and iOS, allowing users to use it anytime, anywhere as a mobile application. Teachers can create classes to manage learning outcomes. All Quizlet users can easily create card sets for free, depending on the vocabulary they need to learn. Students can also contribute to sets created by teachers or compile their own sets of words for learning. Sets consist of terms for lexical items and definitions for descriptions, to which images or sounds can be added.

The electronic application Quizlet has a significant linguodidactic potential in teaching foreign language vocabulary. Its main features include:

1. Variety of exercise formats. Quizlet offers several formats for working with vocabulary: cards, tests, games, as well as the possibility of creating custom word sets. This allows learners to choose the ways of memorising and repeating words that are most convenient for them.

2- Automate the memorisation process. Quizlet's repetition system, based on the principles of interval repetition, helps users memorise foreign language words more effectively. The user programme remembers which words are learned the worst and suggests them for more frequent repetition.

3. Support for different activities. The application supports reading, listening, writing and speaking through a variety of exercises, which helps to develop all types of speech activities. For example, in pronunciation tasks, the user can listen to the correct sound of a word and practise its pronunciation.

4. interactivity and gamification. Through game elements such as speed tests and competitions with other users, the learning process becomes more fun and motivating, which helps to increase interest in learning a foreign language.

5. Accessibility and flexibility. The app is available on different devices and platforms, allowing users to study anywhere and anytime they want. This makes learning more flexible and personalised.

6. Social aspect. Quizlet allows users to share their sets of cards and find cards created by other users. This fosters a learning community where students can share materials and experiences.

Accordingly, at the present stage, digital technologies are increasingly being introduced into the educational processes at universities in Kazakhstan. The use of new technologies in education is primarily driven by pedagogical needs to improve the effectiveness of developmental learning, in particular, the need to develop independent learning skills, research activities, a creative approach to learning, critical thinking, and a new culture [8, pp. 180-189]. In her work, Sarzhanova clearly highlights the pedagogical aspects of using digital technologies in English language teaching, which include selecting appropriate digital tools and platforms, creating interactive and engaging types of work, and providing students with opportunities to practice and receive feedback [9, pp. 429-444]. The use of digital technologies in English language teaching develops all types of speech activity (reading, writing, listening, and speaking).

In his book *Problem-based learning: an approach to medical education*, G. Barrows writes that problem-based learning is a structured approach based on experience and research [10, p. 224]. D. Reine notes that problem-based learning has an instructional strategy in which students encounter conceptually unstructured problems and seek to find meaningful solutions [9, p. 381]. S. Sornberry argues that problem-based learning is purposeful experiential learning organized around the investigation and resolution of complex real-world problems [11, p. 290]. The above definitions of problem-based learning show that this method promotes the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills, and develops the skills of searching for and evaluating independent research.

Participants

The study involved 92 first-year students from M. Utemisov West Kazakhstan University studying foreign languages. The participants ranged in age from 18 to 20. All of them studied English as their main foreign language. The group was divided into two parts: an experimental group (46 students) who worked with vocabulary using the online service Quizlet, and a control group (46 students) who completed traditional tasks from a textbook. The distribution took into account their preliminary level of English proficiency, determined by an entrance test, which allowed the formation of groups with comparable initial results.

Research Questions

1. How effective is the online service Quizlet in developing students' lexical competence when learning English?
2. What types of exercises in Quizlet (e.g., Flashcards, Match, Test) have the greatest impact on the acquisition and consolidation of foreign language vocabulary?
3. How does the use of interactive tasks in Quizlet affect students' motivation and engagement in the process of learning English?

Research Tools

The following tools were used to conduct the study:

1. Entrance and final tests — to measure vocabulary and grammar proficiency before and after the experiment. The tests included translation tasks, multiple-choice questions, fill-in-the-blank exercises, and the use of lexical units in context.
2. Quizlet online service — the main tool in the experimental group. Flashcard sets, Match, Learn, and Test exercises were developed for systematic vocabulary work.
3. Student questionnaires were used to identify participants' attitudes toward using Quizlet, their level of motivation, and their degree of involvement in the learning process.
4. Teacher observation recorded student activity, difficulties encountered, and the nature of interaction during the completion of tasks.

Figure 1. Progress in vocabulary and grammar acquisition in control and experimental groups (percentage increase).

Classes using Quizlet were more interactive and engaging, which helped maintain students' interest and reduced fatigue during work. The use of digital flashcards and game-based tasks created a motivating atmosphere and encouraged active participation in the learning process. Teachers noted that the platform provides convenient tools for tracking individual student progress, identifying gaps in knowledge, and making timely adjustments to teaching.

To assess the effectiveness of Quizlet, diagnostic tests were conducted at the beginning and end of the experiment to identify the level of development of grammatical and lexical skills. During the study, the activities of the students were also observed, and their activity in completing the tasks was systematically recorded.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that the integration of the Quizlet platform into the process of teaching English vocabulary and grammar is both effective and beneficial. Students in the experimental group achieved significantly higher results compared to those taught with traditional methods, showing notable progress in lexical and grammatical competence.

The use of interactive exercises such as flashcards and matching activities not only facilitated better retention of material but also created a motivating and engaging learning environment. Teachers were able to track students' progress more efficiently, identify learning gaps, and provide timely support.

Overall, the study confirms the value of Quizlet as a modern digital tool for foreign language learning and recommends its systematic use in classroom practice to enhance learning outcomes.

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